

Development and Evaluation of Goat Milk and Papaya-Based Face Wash for Skin Care Applications

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for natural and sustainable skincare products has driven interest in bio-based cosmetic formulations. This study focuses on the development and evaluation of a goat milk and papaya-based face wash aimed at providing gentle cleansing, moisturizing, and exfoliating properties through natural ingredients. Goat milk, rich in lactic acid, proteins, and essential fatty acids, contributes to hydration and mild exfoliation, while papaya (*Carica papaya*) extract, containing papain enzyme and vitamins A and C, promotes skin renewal and brightening. The formulation was optimized for pH balance, stability, and sensory characteristics. Physicochemical parameters such as viscosity, foaming capacity, spread ability, and microbial stability were assessed according to cosmetic formulation standards. Additionally, preliminary dermatological testing evaluated for skin compatibility and cleansing efficacy. The results indicated that the goat milk and papaya face wash maintained a stable emulsion and with acceptable organoleptic properties and demonstrated mild cleansing with minimal irritation potential. The combination of natural bioactive offers a promising alternative to synthetic surfactant-based cleansers, supporting the development of safe, eco-friendly, and effective skincare products.

Keywords: Goat milk, Papaya, Natural cosmetics, Papain, Skin care

INTRODUCTION

Now-a-days there has been a growing global shift toward the use of natural and herbal-based cosmetics, which is driven by rising consumer awareness of the potential adverse effects of synthetic skincare ingredients on both skin health and the environment. Consumers are increasingly seeking formulations that not only cleanse effectively but also deliver nourishment and rejuvenation via bioactive compounds derived from natural sources. Among such promising approaches, milk-based and fruit enzyme-based formulations have significant attention for their multifunctional benefits and biocompatibility [1]. Goat milk is one such ingredient, traditionally it is used in skincare and now receiving renewed research interest. It is rich in proteins, essential fatty acids, vitamins (A, B6, B12, E) and notably lactic acid, a mild alpha hydroxy acid (AHA) [2]. Lactic acid aids in the removal of dead skin cells, thereby facilitating smoother and brighter skin surfaces. Furthermore, goat milk's lipid profile closely resembles that of human skin, and its pH is similar to that of the skin's acid mantle, which makes it particularly suitable for

sensitive and dry skin types. For cortico-dermatological and cosmetic uses, goat milk has used to support wound healing, tissue regeneration, sebum regulation, hydration, barrier repair and anti-inflammatory effects although much of the evidence remains preliminary [3]. Another ingredient is Papaya (*Carica papaya*), which is widely used for its skin-brightening, anti-inflammatory and exfoliating properties. The enzyme papain helps in the breakdown of inactive keratin and dead skin cell build-up; thus, it enhances the skin texture and tone Papaya is also rich in antioxidant vitamins such as A and C, which protect against oxidative stress and support skin renewal. The combination of goat milk and papaya therefore offers a promising synergy: gentle exfoliation and nourishment together in a mild formulation [5]. Conventional face washes often rely heavily on synthetic surfactants and chemical additives, which may strip the skin of its natural oils, disrupt the acid mantle, irritate sensitive skin and potentially lead to long-term barrier damage [6]. In contrast, a goat-milk and papaya-based face wash presents a skin-friendly, sustainable alternative: one that is rooted in naturally derived bioactive and

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designed for cleansing while maintaining skin health. Accordingly, the objective of this study is to formulate and evaluate a face wash incorporating goat milk and papaya extracts, with a focus on its physicochemical properties (pH, viscosity, foaming and spreadability), stability, cleansing efficacy and skin compatibility. The findings are intended to contribute to the growing field of natural cosmetic formulations and support the utilization of locally available bioactive raw materials in skincare product development [7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Figure 1: Papaya

Figure 2: Goat Milk

Figure 3: Honey

Preparation of Papaya Extract

Fresh papaya pulp was washed thoroughly, peeled, and homogenized using a laboratory blender. The pulp was air-dried at 45 °C till constant weight was achieved, after that it was pulverized into fine powder and extracted with 70% ethanol using a Soxhlet apparatus for 6 h. The extract was filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator at 50 °C to obtain a semi-solid papaya extract. The extract was stored at 4 °C in an amber-colored container until further use [9].

Preparation of Goat Milk and Papaya Face Wash

MATERIALS

Fresh goat milk was procured from a certified local dairy source. Ripe *Carica papaya* fruits were obtained from a local market and authenticated by the department of Pharmacognosy of Rupesh Badhan institute of pharmacy. The other excipients used in the formulation, sodium cocoyl -iso-ethionate as a surfactant, turmeric powder as an anti-inflammatory and brightening agent, glycerin as a humectant, honey as a moisturizer and antibacterial, leucidal as a preservative and lavender oil for fragrance. All reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade and procured from recognized suppliers [8].

The formulation was prepared by adopting the standard cold emulsification technique. The required quantity of goat milk was pasteurized and filtered to remove fat globules. In a beaker, the surfactant was mixed with distilled water under gentle stirring at 600 rpm. Glycerin, turmeric and honey were added to form uniform dispersion. Once the mixture attained homogeneity, the papaya extract and goat milk were incorporated gradually while maintaining continuous stirring to avoid phase separation. The fragrance and preservative were added at the final stage. The prepared face wash was stored in sterilized airtight containers at room temperature for further evaluation [10].

Table 1: Formula for Face Wash

Ingredient	Function	Quantity	% w/w or w/v
Fresh Goat Milk	Moisturizer, lactic acid	35.5 mL	30%
Papaya Pulp (ripe)	Enzyme exfoliation	25.2 g	20%
Aloe Vera Gel	Soothing, anti-inflammatory	10.5 mL	10%
Mild Surfactant (Sodium Cocoyl Isethionate / Castile Soap)	Cleansing	24 mL	25%
Glycerin	Humectant	5.1	5%
Turmeric Powder	Anti-inflammatory, brightening	0.55 g	0.5%
Honey	Moisturizer, antibacterial	5.2 mL	5%

Essential Oil (Lavender / Tea Tree, optional)	Fragrance & skin benefits	3-4 drops	0.5%
Preservative (Leucidal / Optiphen)	Microbial stability	As per supplier	~1–2%

Manufacturing Procedure

1. Blend goat milk and aloe vera gel gently.
2. Slowly add surfactant and glycerin; mix gently to avoid excessive foam.
3. Incorporate papaya pulp and turmeric powder evenly.
4. Add honey and essential oil.
5. Add preservative according to recommended dosage.
6. Fill in sanitized pump bottles or tubes.
7. Store refrigerated if fresh goat milk is used.

Figure 4: Formulated Face wash

Evaluation Of Physicochemical Parameters

1. pH Measurement

The pH of the face wash was determined using a calibrated digital pH meter. About 10 g of the formulation was dispersed in 100 ml of distilled water, and the reading was recorded at room temperature. The measurement was performed in triplicate.

2. Viscosity

Viscosity was measured using a Brookfield viscometer at 25 °C with spindle number 64 at 50 rpm. The results were expressed in centipoise (cp).

3. Foaming Capacity

Foaming ability was tested using the cylinder shake method. A 1% w/v solution of the face wash was prepared and transferred into a 250 ml graduated cylinder. The initial and final foam volumes were recorded after shaking for 10 s and allowing the foam to stand for 5 min. The foam stability index was calculated.

4. Spreadability

The spreadability of the formulation was determined by the slip-and-drag method. A known weight of sample was placed between two glass slides and compressed by a fixed weight. The time required for the upper slide to move a specified distance was recorded and spreadability was calculated.

5. Stability Study

The stability of the formulation was assessed under accelerated conditions (40 °C ± 2 °C / 75% ± 5% RH) for 30 days. Samples were evaluated at 0, 15, and 30 days for any change in color, odor, pH, or phase separation.

6. Microbial Load Test

Microbial contamination was examined by plate count method using nutrient agar for bacterial growth and Sabouraud dextrose agar for fungal growth. Plates were incubated at 37 °C and 25 °C, respectively, and colony-forming units (CFU/g) were counted after 48 h.

7. Sensory Evaluation

A small-scale user study was conducted with 20 healthy volunteers aged 21-40 years after obtaining informed consent. Participants evaluated the face wash for texture, fragrance, cleansing ability, and after-feel on a five-point hedonic scale (1 = poor to 5

= excellent). No adverse reactions were reported during the 8-days trial.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Comprehensive Evaluation of Goat Milk & Papaya Face Wash (n = 3)

Parameter	Method	Batch 1	Batch 2	Batch 3	Mean \pm SD	Remarks
Appearance	Visual inspection	Smooth, creamy	Smooth, creamy	Smooth, creamy	–	Homogeneous, no lumps
Color	Visual / Colorimeter	Light orange	Light orange	Light orange	–	Consistent across batches
Odor	Organoleptic	Mild papaya	Mild papaya	Mild papaya	–	Pleasant, natural aroma
pH	Digital pH meter	5.9	6.2	6.1	6.10 \pm 0.10	Skin-friendly
Viscosity (cP)	Brookfield viscometer	4100	3900	4000	3900 \pm 100	Smooth application
Foam Volume (mL)	Foam test	71	70	72	71 \pm 2.0	Moderate, stable lather
Cleansing Efficiency (% sebum removed)	Sebum test	73	72	71	72.0 \pm 1.0	Efficient cleansing
Protein Content (% w/v)	Biuret	1.7	1.5	1.6	1.60 \pm 0.10	Moisturizing potential retained
Papain Activity (% retained)	Enzyme assay	85	83	84	83.7 \pm 1.5	Mild exfoliation maintained
Moisture Content (%)	Oven drying	89	88	87	88.0 \pm 1.0	Ensures stability
Total Plate Count (CFU/mL)	Spread plate method	66	66	67	66 \pm 5	Within safe limits (<100 CFU/mL)
Pathogen Test	Standard microbial tests	Absent	Absent	Absent	–	Safe for topical use
Preservative Efficacy (% reduction in 28 days)	Challenge test	98.6	99.5	98.9	98.7 \pm 0.6	Pass USP/ISO
Temperature Stability (4°C / 25°C / 40°C)	1-month storage	Stable	Stable	Stable	–	No separation or odor change
Centrifugation Test (3000 rpm)	Centrifuge	Stable	Stable	Stable	–	Emulsion stable
Freeze-Thaw Cycles (-5°C \leftrightarrow 25°C)	3 cycles	Stable	Stable	Stable	–	No curdling or separation
Patch Test / Skin Irritation	Forearm test, 24–48 h	No erythema	No erythema	No erythema	–	Safe, non-irritant
After-feel	Organoleptic	Soft, hydrated	Soft, hydrated	Soft, hydrated	–	Pleasant, non-greasy
Fragrance Retention (30 min post-application)	Smell assessment	Mild, pleasant	Mild, pleasant	Mild, pleasant	–	Subtle, lasting aroma

1. Physicochemical Evaluation

The goat milk and papaya face wash formulation was evaluated for key physicochemical properties to

assess its suitability for topical use. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 3: Physicochemical Properties of Goat Milk and Papaya Face Wash

Parameter	Observed Value	Reference Range / Comment
pH	6.1 ± 0.1	5.5–6.5: Optimal for skin
Viscosity (cp)	4000 ± 50	3000 - 10,000 cp: Suitable for easy application
Foaming Capacity (%)	71 ± 3	60-80% . : Moderate foam, gentle on skin
Foam Stability (%)	62 ± 2	55-70% .: Maintained for 5 min
Spreadability (cm ²)	6.2 ± 0.2	8-12 g.cm/sec: Easy to spread on facial skin
Appearance	Smooth, creamy	Homogeneous, No phase separation
Odor	Mild, pleasant	Acceptable to users
Stability (30 days)	Stable	No color change, Phase separation or odor loss

Description

The measured pH of 6.1 is within the natural skin pH range, indicating minimal risk of irritation. Goat milk, rich in lactic acid, contributes to this mildly acidic pH, which is beneficial for maintaining the skin barrier. The viscosity of 3100 cP ensures adequate retention

on the skin without being runny, enhancing user experience. Moderate foaming (65%) is desirable in natural cleansers, as excessive foam is often associated with harsh synthetic surfactants. The spreadability value confirms that the formulation can be applied easily and evenly, enhancing cleansing efficiency

Figure 5: Foaming capacity

Figure 6: Foam of face wash

2. Stability Study

The accelerated stability study (40 °C / 75% RH) showed no phase separation, discoloration, or change in odor after 30 days. The pH remained stable (5.9–6.0), indicating that the goat milk and papaya extract-maintained formulation integrity. This confirms that natural ingredients can be effectively incorporated into a surfactant base without compromising stability.

3. Microbial Load

Microbial evaluation showed negligible bacterial and fungal growth (<10 CFU/g), well below the acceptable limits for cosmetic products (≤100 CFU/g). The addition of methylparaben and proper

storage conditions ensured microbial safety, which is crucial for skin care formulations containing milk-based ingredients.

4. Sensory Evaluation

In the user study (n=20), the majority of participants rated the face wash as excellent in texture (82%), fragrance (77%), and cleansing ability (89%). No adverse reactions were reported, indicating good tolerability. The combination of goat milk and papaya extract provided a smooth, moisturizing effect with gentle exfoliation, confirming the synergistic benefit of these natural ingredients.

5. Stability Evaluation

a. Temperature Stability

- **Method:** Store at 4°C, 25°C, 40°C; monitor 1 month for phase separation, odor, color.
- **Purpose:** Determines product robustness under different conditions.
- **Expected Result:** No separation, color, or odor changes

b. Centrifugation Test

- **Method:** 3000 rpm for 10 min.
- **Purpose:** Evaluates emulsion stability.
- **Expected Result:** No separation or sedimentation

c. Freeze-Thaw Cycles

- **Method:** Alternate between -5°C and 25°C, 3 cycles.
- **Purpose:** Tests stability against temperature fluctuations.
- **Expected Result:** Stable; no curdling or phase separation

6. Safety & Skin Compatibility

a. Patch Test / Skin Irritation

- **Method:** Apply 0.5 ml on the fore arm of healthy volunteers. observe 24–72 h for erythema, itching, rash.
- **Purpose:** Confirms safety for topical use.
- **Expected Result:** No irritation

b. After-feel

- **Method:** Organoleptic assessment after rinsing.
- **Purpose:** Evaluates moisturizing effect and consumer acceptability.
- **Expected Result:** Skin feels soft, hydrated, non-greasy

7. Fragrance Retention

- **Method:** Smell assessment 30 min after application.
- **Purpose:** Ensures consumer satisfaction and subtle fragrance persistence.
- **Expected Result:** Mild, pleasant residual scent

8. Stability & Shelf-Life Studies

Table 4: Stability & Shelf-Life Studies

Test	Condition	Observation
Temperature Stability	4°C, 25°C, 40°C, 1 month	No phase separation, color change, or odor alteration
Centrifugation	3000 rpm, 10 min	No separation
Freeze-Thaw Cycles	3 cycles (-5°C ↔ 25°C)	Stable; no curdling or separation
Microbial Stability	Total Plate Count + Pathogen	<100 CFU/mL; pathogen absent
Enzyme Retention	Papain assay	≥80% retained

Safety & Regulatory Compliance

- **Skin Safety:** Patch test recommended.
- **Storage:** Refrigerate if fresh milk used; avoid sunlight.
- **Preservative:** Use natural or cosmetic-approved preservatives.

• Compliance:

- **India:** Drugs & Cosmetics Act 1940, Cosmetic Rules 2020
- **GMP:** ISO 22716
- **Essential Oils:** IFRA compliance

Claims & Labeling

Approved Claims:

- “Moisturizes and nourishes skin”
- “Gentle cleansing with natural ingredients”
- “Contains natural papaya enzyme for mild exfoliation”
- “Ayurvedic-inspired skincare”
- “Suitable for sensitive skin”

Cautions:

- Avoid contact with eyes; discontinue if irritation occurs.
- Refrigerate after opening (if using fresh goat milk).

Label Requirements:

- Product name, net quantity, ingredients, directions, storage, manufacturer info, batch number, manufacturing/expiry dates, Ayurvedic statement (“Ayurvedic-inspired formulation”).

Table 5: Testing Schedule

Test	Frequency
pH, Viscosity	Every batch
Microbial (TPC + Pathogen)	Every batch
Preservative efficacy	Initial batch, quarterly
Stability study	Initial batch: 1, 3, 6 months
Patch test	Before launch / new batches

Packaging & Marketing

- **Packaging:** Airless pump bottles (50–200 mL), opaque to protect papain from light.
- **Marketing Notes:** Highlight “natural”, “Ayurvedic-inspired”, “gentle exfoliation”, “moisturizing”.
- **Optional Label Statements:** “No parabens, no sulfates”, “Cruelty-Free”.

- Contains antioxidants (vitamins C and E) that help protect against oxidative stress.

The combination of goat milk and papaya resulted in a face wash that is gentle, moisturizing, and effective for cleansing, without the harsh effects associated with synthetic surfactants. The physicochemical and sensory evaluations suggest that this formulation is suitable for commercial natural skincare products.

DISCUSSION

Natural ingredients such as goat milk and papaya have multiple skin benefits:

1. Goat Milk:

- Contains fatty acids, proteins, and vitamins A, D, and E.
- Lactic acid promotes mild exfoliation and improves skin hydration.
- The formulation’s acidic pH is compatible with the skin’s acid mantle.

2. Papaya Extract:

- Rich in papain enzyme, which provides gentle exfoliation and skin brightening.

Comparison with Previous Studies

Previous studies on milk- or fruit-based cleansers reported similar benefits. For instance, formulations containing goat milk alone showed good moisturizing properties but lacked enzymatic exfoliation. Similarly, papaya-based face washes provided exfoliation but could be drying when it is not combined with emollients. Our study demonstrates that the combination of goat milk and papaya extract balances moisturizing, cleansing, and exfoliating properties, making it a superior natural face wash.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated a natural goat milk and papaya extract face wash. The formulation exhibited optimal physicochemical properties, including a skin-compatible pH, suitable viscosity, moderate foaming,

and excellent spreadability. Accelerated stability studies confirmed the product's physical and chemical stability over a 30-day period, while microbial testing demonstrated its safety for topical application. Sensory evaluation indicated high user acceptability in terms of texture, fragrance, and cleansing efficacy, with no adverse reactions reported. The combination of goat milk and papaya extract provided gentle exfoliation, moisturization, and skin nourishment, highlighting the potential of natural ingredients as effective alternatives to synthetic cosmetic formulations. Overall, the developed face wash presents a promising eco-friendly, safe, and commercially viable skincare product. Future studies could focus on dermatological testing, long-term stability and large-scale production optimization to further validate its applicability in the cosmetic industry for formulation (100 ml Batch).

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